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FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS FORUM

EVENT REPORT

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CREATING PARTNERSHIPS TO ADVANCE POLICY KNOWLEDGE OF PEOPLE ON THE MOVE

Report

Proposal

Who we are:

The InterAgency Institute is dedicated to research in security issues, such as border control, interagency schemes, and cooperation frameworks, especially those involving complex scenarios, policy building, and governance. Our proposal aims at enhancing collaboration in developing ideas for a more effective multistakeholder approach in dealing with migration crises, adopting a people-centered approach and a youth perspective. Under the Fundamental Rights Forum 2021 is the creating partnerships through inter-agency cooperation and promoting knowledge of people in transit policies. We focus mainly on youth integration policies and optimizing communication so that a wider audience can be reached.

Theme: Creating partnerships to advance policy knowledge of people on the move

- 1 session remotely organized as Teams Meetings.
- Public Meetings.

Specific details:

Session

○ Time frame: Mon, 11 OCT 2021 at 13:30h-14:30h UTC

○ Audience: Global (students from USSG, researchers)

○ Method:

Part 1 = Moderator opening and presentation of rules and panelists + 3-4 min for each panelist (4 in total)

Part 2 = Interaction with the public and wrap-up

Language: English

○ Participants:

Dr Sabrina Medeiros, Portugal (panelist and wrap-up)

Dr Lygia Hryniewicz, Germany (panelist)

Dr Luzia Becker, Germany (panelist)

Ms Ana Beatriz Duarte, Portugal (moderator and panelist)

Dr Ana Paula Rodriguez, Spain/Brazil (Backstage/midia)

Abstract

The session was dedicated to discussing forms of policies adaptive conditions, knowledge interoperability, and EU directives compliance concerning people on move. We believe that policies' enhancement is dependent on links within them, accessibility, and visibility, boosting human rights compliance, opportunities, and migrants integration. The session will be organized into two phases: governed by environmental scanning, and after, by horizon scanning. The analysis means to be made based on a multistakeholder approach to promote the complete cycle of ambiance detection and prospects for policy adaptation. The first step is planned to creating visibility on the participant's experiences and known good practices. The second step is committed to the desired outcomes that can be implemented to various populations in transit governance adaptive demands.

Objectives – The session will consider specificities around gender and youth perspectives, according to the recent EU statement on the importance of third parties cooperation.

Consult / brainstorm with other HR actors/operators

Influence, challenge or support policy making with concrete proposals and solutions

Launch or promote a campaign, initiative, product (ex. publication, report, project results) using the Forum as a prominent platform

Expected outcomes - In addition, the session sought the possibility of creating partnerships for the advancement of knowledge portals to promote visibility of policies and integration demands and opportunities for people on the move, with a focus on language defense with the EU.

Building capacity and mutual improvement of skills and knowledge

Build or foster partnerships - synergies

Identify and/or flag a critical issue/problem/challenge

Keywords: Migration, Humanitarian, Interagency, Youth

Session - Executive Summary

Interagency frameworks for the benefit of people on the move

Sabrina Medeiros, PhD

Interagency schemes are indispensable, and efficiency is the new boundary when we consider complex operations involving immigrants. Significant improvements are associated with interoperability practices, but the operational level is not the only one that misses cooperative efforts. Migration has been a theme with a massive impact on human rights, marked by the interagency security policies which effect may overlap other demanded schemes.

Thus, some experiences may be cited as examples of managing emergent and constant flows of people, apprehend and systematize good practices. Although some countries may receive important flows of migrants, within its own borders, migrants may not achieve the conditions for sustaining themselves due to second stage measures failure for inclusion, whereas the destiny may come only an entrepôt (1). Policies are dependent, so, to crossing borders and understanding the nature and signs of dimensioning of flows.

Plataforma R4V (*Plataforma Regional de Coordenação Interagencial de Resposta a Refugiados e Migrantes da Venezuela*) is an interagency framework that gathers around 50 international agencies and non-governmental organizations (2). The impressive numbers the *Acolhida Operation* shows are better observed through the portal in which it is possible to access documents, reports, maps, and communication statements, making results visible. At the same time, less has been done for the migrants access to useful information. However, participative diagnostics are one of the most expressive outputs ACNUR achieved in the region (2020/2021), marking a initiative with more than 600 participants and 118 groups of discussion. Finally, the interiorization policy marks the relevant numbers civil-military interagency efforts showed by an interactive permanent portal (3).

The Danish Refugee Council created through the Mixed Migration Centre the 4Mi methodology for globalized system of collecting primary data on mixed migration flows. Based on migrants interviews, outputs and analysis from the 4Mi guarantees the view of the big picture (snapshot, as they are called), but remains not serving as a tool for the migrants (4). Questions and results are more dedicated to the identification of routes and motivators than prospects for the migrants groups.

At the International Organization for Migration (IOM) level, the Global Migration Group was an interagency initiative to foster policy compliance and diffusion into agents and stakeholders, substituted by the United Nations Network on Migration, following-up and reviewing of the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration (GCM). Anchored by the UN Development Assistance Frameworks (UNDAFs) “to ensure strong national ownership”, it is still not accessible to migrants communities. The Migration Network Hub includes materials such as the 4Mi provides and seems to boost projects already in place, but not more than that.

To frame how practices can uphold experience in policy building, we give a unique lens on bottom-up analysis as a way to spread initiatives and mark policy diffusion. Another essential element to be considered is that, in general, practices that involve Global South countries as receiving actors do not reach the international regimes policy component. On the other side, there are significant pressures mainly from the Global North, which characterize the increasing externalization of the border and visa control (5).

As it seems, different dimensions may conflict with each other, and my proposal is that a significant part of the interoperability aspects is massively undertaken, especially those that cross the levels of interagency processes. I propose a matrix to look for the various *levels* (X) and *dimensions* (Y) to analyze the migration policy management systems.

As *levels* (X), I consider the different drivers of migration policies and institutional frameworks: field level (a), an operational and management level (b), specific policy framework level (c), and a regime or international push-up level (d).

On the other side, as to *dimensions* (Y), I state that the interagency schemes are of different nature, and it conditions their outreaching. That is the way the definition of limits in between them is complex: security dimension (defense and security scopes), social dimension (assistance and inclusion policies and impacts), political dimension (legal status).

Behind this scene, the need for adaptive institutions to be built way forward. There arises the most crucial gearing element, transparency. Transparency may be a way to guarantee informing communities of migrants and mark policy comprehensiveness throughout various nodes and agents of the network. So, efforts should be concentrated in:

- Mapping nodes and networks.
- Orienting governance as a service, from whom to who.
- Observing gaps and building a permanent channel to denunciation.

- Promoting channels to inform and be informed by economic opportunities for migrant inclusiveness, using local networks enabled by autarchies.

Gathering different initiatives and recommendations under progress, I acknowledge it progresses on the recognition that policy development cannot surpass interagency barriers without (tech)knowledge (6).

References:

- (1) Natalia Cintra. Visa Policies as Externalisation Practices in the Global South. OCT 2021. <https://www.e-ir.info/pdf/94318>
- (2) <https://brazil.iom.int/news/plataforma-r4v-e-o-trabalhado-humanit%C3%A1rio-na-opera%C3%A7%C3%A3o-acolhida>; <https://www.r4v.info/pt/brazil>;
- (3) <http://aplicacoes.mds.gov.br/snas/painel-interiorizacao/>
- (4) <https://mixedmigration.org/resource/4mi-snapshot-access-to-information-among-refugees-and-migrants-in-mexico/>
- (5) Migrações, Fronteiras e Desenvolvimento JAN/FEV 2017 número 12. Número 11, Revista Da Plataforma Portuguesa Das ONGD. <https://www.plataformaongd.pt/uploads/revistas/revista-12-plataformaongd-migracoes-jan-fev-2017.pdf>
- (6) Dominik Hangartner, Zurich Bilal Malaeb, Angelo Martelli. Human Mobility: Towards Enhanced Integration and Social Cohesion. Policy brief Task Force 10 Migration. T20 2021. https://www.t20italy.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/TF10_PB03_LM02.pdf

The two Ps toward better policies: participation and partnerships

Ana Beatriz Duarte, MsC

One of the central features of the latest European Union Action Plan on Migrants' Integration and Inclusion [1] for the next six years is to enhance migrants' **participation**.

This means a bottom-up approach is institutionally desired. For this purpose, an Expert Group was created within the European Commission in order to listen and incorporate the views of the very subjects of migration policies.

It intends that this participation be not only more intense among migrants but also wider, including those EU citizens with migrant backgrounds.

That makes sense. As we all know, migration was and is central to the very meaning of the European Union, and so is, of course, the policymaking related to it.

Furthermore, it is a big step towards the understanding of migrant policies as policies that will ultimately affect everyone. That is, that policies for migrants are policies for all.

In fact, many governments aim, at least in theory, at citizen participation. But not seldom blame the population for poor results when it comes to engagement with participatory tools and channels they create, sometimes in one-sided decisions. What can be done to improve participation then?

Policymaking is not restricted to public administration. In reality, it involves a much more complex network of stakeholders. Between policymakers and the subjects of the policies they make, there are many less visible actors.

Civil society is among them. Some sectors under the umbrella of civil society are: companies, the media, academics, and other research institutes, like think tanks. It is indeed a key stakeholder for the success of migrant's integration policies. Something that the Covid pandemic has made even clearer.

As Mr. Michael O'Flaherty [2], Director of the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights has stated, **partnerships** between policymakers and practitioners are something the Human Rights agenda cannot do without.

[3]

The political agenda is shaped by decision-makers in connection with public opinion, which in turn can be influenced by third parties. Institutions other than government may play a role in different stages of the policymaking process. They may raise awareness and call attention of the public to a certain issue (agenda setting), advocate and influence for change, provide information and evidence, promote dialogue, and even draft policy in some cases. Not less important, civil society groups have shown to be central in the implementation as well as in the monitoring stages.

[3]

Because we understand that broader participation cannot be achieved without better communication, we support the OECD’s recommendation on How best to communicate on migration and integration prepared with a special focus on the after-pandemic context: I quote: “Pre-established partnerships with NGOs, journalists or local authorities improve governments’ capacities to adapt their communication approach/strategy towards immigrants” [4].

The same OECD paper goes further on specific tips to engage with migrants: the use of multiple languages and formats, including non-digital, accessibility, tackling misinformation, and — avoiding a very common mistake —: consider migrants as a homogeneous group, instead of considering the diversity of several specific audiences with something in common: the search for a better life through mobility.

These are all undoubtedly true for public and collective communication activities. But our messaging today concentrates on an underlying, precondition to all these other needs: active listening. Communication is not a one-way street. No form of communication will be effective without understanding the audience. Too basic as it may seem, this old-known axiom is too often forgotten. Indeed, governments are too far from policy subjects to be able to really get to know them. That’s where mediation actors like scholars and NGOs play, though not central, still a crucial role.

The Portuguese scholar Boaventura Sousa Santos [5] advocates, after a concept taken from the Brazilian educator Paulo Freire, that researchers should research and write not ABOUT the subjects they investigate but rather WITH THEM. This is a huge switch in thinking, that breaks hierarchy among parts and recognises the populations as authors of equally valued knowledge. May this mindset be also adopted by policymakers and all those stakeholders dealing with human rights policies.

References

- [1] EUROPEAN COMMISSION. Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027 in Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions. Link available at https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/pdf/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf.
- [2] Fundamental Rights Forum (2021). Fundamental Rights Forum 2021: what to expect and look forward to? 22 Jul 2021. Available at : <https://fundamentalrightsforum.eu/news/posts/fundamental-rights-forum-2021-what-to-expect-and-look-forward-to/>
- [3] ANDERSSON, Thomas (2019). Revised Code of Good Practice for Civil Participation in the Decision-making Process. Council of Europe.
- [4] OECD (2020). How best to communicate on migration and integration in the context of Covid-19. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/how-best-to-communicate-on-migration-and-integration-in-the-context-of-covid-19-813bddfb/>
- [5] SANTOS, Boaventura de Sousa; MENESES, Maria Paula. (Orgs.) (2010). Epistemologias do Sul. São Paulo; Editora Cortez.

After the two presentations, a question was created so that the audience could Interact:

- How interagency schemes can evolve and what can civil society actors do to improve active listening of migrant populations?

The European Union and the challenge of integration: from the bottom up

Luzia Costa Becker, PhD

As a supranational entity, the European Union has no specific legal competence for integration policies, and it is up to the member states to define them.

However, in order to establish a common strategic framework that might help member states further develop and strengthen their national integration policies, several measures have been taken in the last two decades as this timeline shows.

EUROPEAN COMMISSION (2021). Migrant Integration Information and good practices.

The action plans published, starting in 2016, when, according to European Commission data, there were 20 million third-country nationals residing in the European Union, which represented 4 % of its total population.

Published in June 2016, the first European Action Plan on the Integration of Third-Country Nationals covered several policy areas, at European Union and Member State level, from the following policy priorities:

- pre-departure or pre-arrival measures (providing information and language skills);
- education;
- integration into the labor market and access to vocational training;
- access to basic services (housing, health) and
- active participation and social inclusion.

The 2016 Plan comprehended actions for each of these five policy priorities and for instruments for coordinating, financing, and monitoring it, briefly listing measures and the main actors of these measures.

The local plans drawn up and the actions taken have made a positive contribution on improving the integration of third-country nationals in all European Union member states.

However, according to the Commission, some shortcomings and areas for improvement have emerged during their implementation. These include the lack of data and structured monitoring systems, and the difficulty of access to specific segments of the population.

In this way, the second Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027, published in November 2020, addresses cross-cutting issues such as promoting partnerships between key integration stakeholders, fighting racism and discrimination, optimizing the use and impact of European Union funding on integration and inclusion, using digital tools and monitoring progress in delivering integration and inclusion policies based on reliable data.

EUROPEAN COMMISSION (2021). Migrant Integration Information and good practices.

The Plan also considers the specific needs of different groups, among them, European Union citizens with a migration background, women, religious minorities, and people with disabilities.

In this process, the involvement of the host society is of great importance.

Also in this process, local and regional authorities play a key role in designing and implementing efficient, sustainable and replicable integration programs.

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EUROPEAN COMMISSION. Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027 in Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European

Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions. Link available at

https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/pdf/action_plan_on_integration_and_inclusion_2021-2027.pdf.

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Site on Integration – Migrant Integration Information and good practices. Link available at <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/public/the-eu-and-integration/framework>.

Integration and qualification for youth migrants workers

Lygia Hryniewicz, PhD

In Europe the working-age population (15-64) is projected to decline by 7.5 million (-2.2%) between 2013 and 2020, while it will grow in the same proportion in the OECD area as a whole. Under a scenario with zero net migration, the working-age population of the 28 EU countries would be expected to decline by even more, i.e. 11.7 million (-3.5%) by 2020. Under this scenario, Germany, Italy and Poland would each lose more than 1.5 million people of working age by 2020.

As the structure of the economy changes, a considerable amount of net occupational change occurs through the entry of young workers and the exit of older workers.

It is often argued that this decline should be offset to avoid lower economic growth and wellbeing, and that this requires additional workers, including immigrants, to move into the occupations from which older workers are retiring. The picture, however, is not so simple. First, in many countries, there is still considerable slack in the labour market, not only with respect to open unemployment but also regarding low labour market participation of women, older workers, and other groups such resident immigrants and their children. Secondly, workers are extending their working lives, which contributes to increasing the size of the labour force.

Significant numbers of immigrant entries are observed in both growing and declining occupations, however, immigrants make up for only a fraction of total movements into these occupations. In Europe, over the past decade, new immigrants represented 15% of

entries into strongly growing occupations, such as science, technology and engineering as well as the health and education professions.

Large numbers of workers retiring from an occupation do not necessarily imply that many immigrants will have to be recruited to make up for the (apparent) shortfall in youth entries, nor does a significant inflow of youth into strongly growing occupations obviate the need for recruitment from abroad. Recruitment needs depend on the precise nature of labour demand, and this is difficult to predict over the medium term.

Free movement is one of the four fundamental freedoms in the European Union but it is also an underused economic resource. From an economic standpoint, as pointed out in the seminal work of Mundell (1961), labour mobility has a key role to play as a shock absorber within a currency union. Given the disparate labour market conditions prevalent across the EU, mobility within the EU could indeed act as a significant re-equilibrating force thereby contributing to employment growth.

One thing that calls attention is that: the most widely used and readily available proxy for skills is educational attainment. For example, immigrants tend to be overrepresented at both ends of the qualification scale and, in Europe, have on average slightly fewer years of education than the native-born. Relative to their native-born peers, immigrants in the United States have lower education levels than immigrants in Europe. At the same time, one observes that in both regions, immigrants who have arrived more recently are more highly educated than immigrants who arrived years ago. Immigrants who have arrived recently also have almost the same number of years of education as the native-born of the same age and gender living in the same country, particularly in Europe. This holds independent of origin countries and is a strong indication of a changing pattern of migration flows towards more qualified migration.

Reference

<https://www.oecd.org/els/mig/OECD-EC%20Migration%20Policy%20Brief%2009-2014.pdf>

After the last presentations, the second question was prepared for the audience:

- How to build integration policies in line with young migrant populations in terms of interaction and adaptability tools? For example what can be done in terms of job market?

Wrap-Up

Afterwards, teacher Sabrina Medeiros conducted the Wrap-up, organizing and connecting the ideas of all panelists. At this time, the questions raised in the session were also answered.